

SOCIAL EQUALITY AND ECONOMIC STABILITY AS A FACTOR IN CREATING A WELFARE STATE

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Abstract. *The given article presents the theory of building a social state, the reflection of the principles of a social state in the legislation of countries around the world and Uzbekistan, as well as the strategy of social reforms carried out in Uzbekistan to ensure human rights and freedoms.*

Keywords: *social equality, economic sustainability, welfare state, constitution, human rights and freedom, national and universal values, social protection, strategy, poverty reduction.*

It is important to suggest that in the history of mankind, the struggle for social equality has led to the formation of democratic systems, the reform movement and the creation of welfare states. Social equality and economic stability have become an important factor influencing the development of society and shaping its future.

The welfare state is a state model that creates a decent way of life for every citizen based on the principles of social equality and justice, and pursues a fair policy of assistance to those in need. Therefore, it is important to eliminate the following problems on the way to the formation of the welfare state:

- Lack of resources to finance social programs;
- social inequality;
- corruption and excessive bureaucratic practice;
- low quality of social services;
- political instability, internal and external conflicts;
- the negative impact of international economic trends and globalization on social programs.

Each of these problems requires a comprehensive approach and cooperation between the state and society.

History of the emergence of the theory of the welfare state

Everyone knows that the concept of the welfare state first appeared in the 19th century. The studies of German scientists Lorenz von Stein, F. Naumann, A. Wagner, J. Offner. L. von Stein express the mission of the welfare state at the administrative level in two main tasks (firstly, in ensuring free movement between classes, secondly, in helping the disadvantaged) and show how these tasks are realized in individual administrative functions of the state:

Elimination of legal barriers to free movement between classes; satisfaction of social needs aimed at providing the necessary physical conditions for the freedom of each person; helping non-capitalized labor to become economically independent. [5].

L. von Stein explains the essence of the welfare state as follows: "The state is obliged to maintain absolute equality of rights for all different social classes, for a person who defines himself through his power, to support the economic and social development of all citizens." "[5].

Stein's theory is a classical theory that considers the state as the only guarantor of social justice. According to A. E. Evstratov, although the modern interpretation of the concept of a social

state is very different from the theory of L. von Stein, research in this regard should be based on its definition. The reason is that in his theory Stein emphasized the priority of the relations "man-state" instead of the previous relations "society-state" and declared that the main goal of the state is economic and social development [6].

In general, L. von Stein's theory of the social state serves not only as a set of new methods of public administration, but also as a model of state activity at a certain stage of development.

Uzbekistan - a social and secular state

Surprisingly, the countries that were the first to enshrine social rights in their constitutions are the United States of Mexico and Germany. Currently, the countries of Europe, Asia, America and many other regions have the status of a welfare state.

The concept of a social state has its essence in the history, culture and customs of our national statehood. Having received the status of a social state, Uzbekistan has undertaken to create the necessary conditions for the comfortable living of every citizen. In the center of state policy, ensuring the individual and his interests was defined as a priority task.

It is important to suggest that in the Address of the President to Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, it was emphasized that New Uzbekistan should be built on the principle of a social state and it was enshrined in the Constitution. As a result, the principle "First - the individual, then - society and the state" is reflected in the Constitution and socio-economic reforms implemented in our country.

Article 1 of our Constitution, written on the basis of national and universal values, provides for the minimum welfare of the state for its citizens, a social state and norms of solidarity; in Article 19, benefits are provided on the basis of legal documents; in Article 20, in the event of a contradiction or ambiguity in matters not clearly defined in the legislation, the issue is resolved in favor of the person; honor and dignity of a person, norms of personal freedom are expressed in Article 26; Ensuring human rights and freedoms as the highest goal of the state was enshrined in Article 54, and the norms of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for all segments of the population were strengthened by Article 57. [1]. The new Constitution also enshrines 90 human rights, which include life, honor, dignity and freedom.

Social reforms - for people

It is not a secret that defining the social state, the head of state paid attention to such aspects as equal opportunities for people to realize their potential, creating the necessary conditions for a decent life for people, reducing poverty. In this regard, systemic reforms were carried out, social protection was updated in form and content based on international experience and scientific methodologies, formed as a single centralized system, quality control was established.

Implementation of a comprehensive system of professional social protection;

Ensuring the socialization of the population in need of assistance;

Organization of social protection to the microdistrict level;

Expanding the coverage of the population with social insurance mechanisms;

Preventing families from falling into a difficult social situation by providing comprehensive social services;

The creation of a comfortable environment for people with disabilities are defined by the state as the main direction of targeted protection of the population. [2].

Also, the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created, in 208 districts (cities) social protection centers "Inson" and social work

were deployed; [2]. Based on the main activities of this agency, a system for providing more than 100 social services and assistance to 12 categories of families in need of social protection has been created at the district level;

2,429 people in need of care have been identified and entered into the register of single or lonely people;

1,852 paid services for the provision of social and household services, support or supervision have been organized;

10,169 disabled people have been assigned a disability group;

the types of rehabilitation technical means and prosthetic and orthopedic devices have been increased from 18 to 30, and the amount of reimbursed funds has been increased by an average of 10 times;

it became possible to select the necessary tools electronically;

3,300 disabled people willing to work have been accepted for vacancies in state organizations through an open competition;

In 66 specialized preschool and school educational institutions, "Care" groups have been created, they include 255 children with severe disabilities;

It is known to everyone that over the past 5 years, more than 3 thousand people, this year 642 orphans and children left without parental care were provided with housing; maintaining a register of low-income families in the area of microdistricts and working with each family in the register based on individual programs.

Welfare state issues in the strategy "Uzbekistan-2030"

The strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" was approved in order to ensure a free and prosperous life for the people of Uzbekistan, create equal opportunities for everyone to develop their potential, form a strong economy, ensure justice and the rule of law, security and stability. Based on the main ideas of the strategy, to take a place among countries with an above-average income due to stable economic growth; formation of an education system, medical and social protection that fully complies with international standards and the needs of the population; creation of favorable environmental conditions; building a fair and modern state; guarantee of the sovereignty and security of the country; create suitable conditions for each person to realize their potential; conservation of water resources and environmental protection; ensuring the rule of law; organization of public administration in the service of the people; 100 socially significant strategic goals were set, such as the implementation of reforms in the direction of consistent continuation of the policy based on the principle of a "secure and peaceful state". [3]. For example, by implementing reforms in the field of education, Uzbekistan will be included in the list of Top 50 countries of the Global Innovation Index;

doubling the amount of funds allocated for medicine, reducing hereditary diseases in children and the mortality rate of women, infants and children after childbirth by 2 times, 100% digitalization of medical institutions, providing people with disabilities in need with high-quality and modern prosthetic and orthopedic service products.

Besides that, full coverage of those in need of social protection services will be achieved, doubling the employment of people with disabilities, ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of children and women.

It should be mentioned that by 2030, an important factor in sustainable economic growth was identified as a radical reduction in poverty, reducing the unemployment rate to 7%, bringing the gross domestic product to \$ 160 billion, and per capita income to \$ 4,000. [3].

Definitely, the implementation of the goals set in this strategy is of great importance in terms of improving the main areas of development and implementing the principles of the social state in the country.

By summerising it should be suggested that it is permissible to say that in studies on the theory of social state building it is necessary to take into account the importance of determining the forms of relationships between civil society and the social state, between individual freedom and the regulatory function of the state, national and global relations and international economic trends. The main goal of reforms to build a welfare state is the transition from the "state-society-individual" model to the "individual-society-state" model.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (adopted at the referendum on April 30, 2023)
<https://constitution.uz/uz/clause/index>
2. Election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 1, 2023 PR-82
3. Election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 11, 2023 PR-158
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 23, 2024
5. Stein, L. von. The doctrine of management and the right to management with a comparison of the literature and legislation of France, England and Germany. - St. Petersburg: A. S. Hieroglyphs, 1874. - P. 524.
6. Evstratov, A. E. Genesis of the idea of the welfare state (Historical and theoretical problems): dis. cand. law. science. – Omsk, 2005. – P. 11–12.